

IDEA – Mapping of EDI initiatives at the VU Amsterdam & Amsterdam UMC

Name	Institution	Link
Code of Conduct addressing EDI (page 10)	AUMC	https://werkenbij.amsterdamumc.org/CmsData/Bestanden/gedragscode-engelstalig_-_code-of-conduct-english-version---amsterdam-umc-versie-6.pdf
D&I E-magazine with a lot of different initiatives going on (e.g. staff stories, facts and figures, low literacy escape room, podcasts, Culturally Sensitive Care Handbook, zouikwatzeggen app, support centre for gender issues)	AUMC	https://amsterdamumc.foleon.com/diversiteit-en-inclusie/d-and-i-magazine-amsterdam-umc-introductionday/
<p>The Inclusion Explorer – practical reflection method to address morally difficult situations around diversity and inclusion</p> <p>It is based on a previously developed dialogue method: ‘The Diversity Compass’. See also: Kröger, C., Molewijk, B., Muntinga, M., & Metselaar, S. (2024). The Diversity</p>	AUMC	https://werkenbij.amsterdamumc.org/CmsData/Bestanden/UMC001-112_InclusieVerkenner%20A4%20digitaal_engels_03%20(002)%20Def%2025-8-25.pdf

Compass: a clinical ethics support instrument for dialogues on diversity in healthcare organisations. BMC medical ethics, 25(1), 4. https://doi.org/10.1186/s12910-023-00992-z		
Charter Talent to the Top – endorsed by AUMC for more female talent in the top and subtop levels	AUMC	https://talentnaardetop.nl/netwerk/charter-monitor/
Mixed Classroom Educational Model - an educational approach that builds upon differences to enrich the learning experience for all students	VU	https://vu.nl/en/about-vu/more-about/mixed-classroom
Colourful Staff Action Plan - this plan aims to increase the cultural diversity of VU staff in all layers of the organisation. This is done by focusing on the recruitment process, the working environment and the recognition process of staff members who are migrants or child of migrants	VU	https://vu.nl/en/about-vu/more-about/colourful-staff-action-plan
Bonding & Bridging project - this activity teaches students to be open to individual differences, to view the world from a broader	VU	https://vu.nl/en/about-vu/more-about/diversity-projects

perspective and to grow their network		
Decolonisation LAB project – this project inspires us to take a close look at the colonial history of the Netherlands	VU	https://vu.nl/en/about-vu/more-about/diversity-projects
Diversity Calendar – this calendar is a visual overview of important cultural and religious holidays.	VU	https://vu.nl/en/about-vu/more-about/diversity-calendar
Inclusive Curricula project	VU	https://vu.nl/en/about-vu/more-about/diversity-projects
<p>Inclusive Workplaces project – this project aim to develop and implement a structured approach to diversity and inclusion (D&I). Through extensive research and collaboration with employees, we seek to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop a coherent strategy for inclusive workplaces at VU Amsterdam. - Provide a centralized toolbox with accessible interventions that support inclusion at all levels. - Implement soft accountability measures and continuous 	VU	https://vu.nl/en/employee/policy-and-organisation/inclusive-workplaces

monitoring to track progress and ensure effectiveness.		
Diversity Day 2025 - This day invites us to reflect on differences and inclusion. Under the motto “connecting beyond differences”, the national organisation behind Diversity Day emphasises that connectedness and respect for diversity form the foundation of a strong society.	VU	https://vu.nl/en/employee/policy-and-organisation/diversity-day-2025
VU Pride network - VU Pride aims to create a safe and inclusive environment for all individuals of the lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, queer, intersex and asexual (LGBTQIA+) community on our campus.	VU	https://vu.nl/en/about-vu/organisations/vu-pride
WO&MEN@VU network – this is a network of and for VU employees who want to improve gender equality between men and women. WO&MEN@VU consists of people of all gender identities.	VU	https://vu.nl/en/about-vu/organisations/womenvu
FAM – Family of Academic Minds network – this is an inclusive student association that commits to creating a welcoming community for all students.	VU	https://www.befam.nl

Univers network - is the network of neurodivergent VU employees (such as those with ADHD, autism or epilepsy) who seek support, have questions, or want to connect.	VU	https://vu.nl/nl/medewerker/naast-je-werk/univers
Dialogue, Diversity and Debate (3D) - there are meetings about inclusion, diversity and social issues that concern our academic community. In collaboration with the 3D coordinator, students and staff can also suggest topics themselves.	VU	https://vu.nl/en/about-vu/organisations/3d